

Sport and Exercise Behavior of Students in Suan Sunandha Rajabhat University

Authors : Pimporn Thongmuang

Abstract : The purpose of this research is to study sport and exercise behavior of students in Suan Sunandha Rajabhat University in September of 2012. The sample group used in this research was a group of regular students in undergraduate school enrolled in faculty of science and technology. This sample group consisted of 1,858 students. The research tool used to collect result was the checklist. The data was calculated by statistical percentage. From the research, it was discovered that most students did exercise in previous month. 71.6% of students exercised by running. 61.1% of students exercised in their neighborhood. 60.4% of students exercised in order to keep fit. 60.2% of students agreed that the result from this research can be educational and inspirational for students in campus in terms of living healthily by exercise.

Keywords : exercise behavior, sport behavior, students, health

Conference Title : ICPBS 2014 : International Conference on Political and Behavioral Sciences

Conference Location : Prague, Czech Republic

Conference Dates : July 10-11, 2014